

Community Awareness for Competency Based Curriculum, A Case of Parents of Public Secondary School Students in Arusha Tanzania

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Abstract: *The study focuses on the assessment of community awareness for competency based curriculum. The study utilized convenient sampling to collect data from parents of students who are in public secondary school, a total of 50 correspondents in Arusha region where interviewed and given questionnaires. Data were collected by interview and questionnaires. Data from interview were analyzed by thematic analysis and those from questionnaire were analyzed by spss 21. The finding indicates that the community has little awareness about competency based curriculum and their objectives. At the same time the challenge of capital and technology is a factor towards pushing and educating the co teachers who are parents to know about competency based curriculum and they should expect to get from their children.*

Keywords; Competency Based Curriculum, Arusha, Awareness, Community.

1. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF COMPETENCY BASED CURRICULUM IN TANZANIA.

Tanzania became independent from Great Britain in 1961, under the leadership of Mwalimu Julius Nyerere. The country became the location for the most of daring social reform seen on African continent. These reforms were based on the twin principles of socialism and self-reliance.

The country has undergone four changes in educational curriculum since independence. The first changes were made in 1967, this was the first change to be made and its main aim was to change colonial education system, during colonial era Tanzanian were given low quality education to serve their masters, 1967 changes were made as result of political, economical and social change influenced by Arusha declaration of 1967, which came out by education for reliance manifesto, among the changes were made was removing standard eight in primary schools and middle schools in primary school level. The vision for these changes was to fight three enemies which are poverty, diseases and ignorance. The curriculum objectives by this time were:

1. To teach students see themselves as a part of society
2. Education to seed the spirit of living together and working together
3. Education to help children see themselves equally as human being and to remove the gaps and elements of tribalism, religions and racism.
4. To build inquiry skills and self-confidence among students
5. To prepare students for rural works and self-reliance

The second phase of curriculum changes was made in year 1979, these changes were led by the philosophy of education for self-reliance in order to strengthen and

implement the socialism and self reliance. These changes also aimed to put in action the national philosophy by the time which was politics is agriculture and Arusha declaration.

These changes enabled the initiation of secondary schools with wings of business, vocation and agriculture. This curriculum emphasized the equality between theory and practice in teaching and also science and mathematics subjects were given much strength.

The objective of these changes were to prepare modern experts in the fields of agriculture, business and vocation skill in order to rise and liberate the country from economy problems

The third change of curriculum in Tanzania were made in the year 1997. These changes were based on the recommendation of the Makweta commission of 1982. In the year 1982 the President commission of education which was known as Makweta commission give the recommendation about improvement on the education system and the curriculum and also introduction of multiparty in the country was also a factor to the change,

The fourth change was in 2005. In this year government of Tanzania introduced competency based curriculums which led to the development of competency based learning and competency based assessment in secondary education. In 2006, competency based curriculum became operational in both primary and secondary school, There have been serious financial and human commitments to retrain and support teachers, head of schools and other educational professionals to develop the necessary competency and confidence to effectively handle competency based education. Introduction of competency based education is the second major change after independence. In 1967 changes were education for self-reliance. Competence based education involves some pedagogical changes in the curriculum and instructional

approaches to incorporate competency based learning rather than theoretical understanding of concepts.

DRAFT	OBJECTIVE	CHARACTERISTICS
FIRST CHANGE-1967	1.To teach students to see themselves as part of society 2.Education to promote the spirit of living together and working together 3.Education to help children see themselves equally as human being and to remove the gaps and elements of tribalism, religious fundamentalism and racism. 4.To build inquiry skills and self-confidence among students 5.To prepare students for rural works and self-reliance	EDUCATION FOR SELF RELIANCE CURRICULUM
SECOND CHANGE-1979	1.Develop specialized schools for agriculture and business 2.To remove standard eight from the school system 3.Develop more vocational colleges. 4.Prepare modern experts in the field of agriculture and business.	EDUCATION FOR SELF RELIANCE CURRICULUM
THIRD CHANGE-1997	1.Introduce multi-partism in syllabus. 2.Introduction of civics,general studies and development studies in secondary schools and universities	EDUCATION FOR SELF RELIANCE CURRICULUM
FOURTH CHANGE-2005	1.To help students acquire experience and knowledge in their lives, □curriculum designer provides an experience that will tap learners’ values and ideas, (ii)To help □learners experience new situations and match new experience with previous learning, learners distill new values and new knowledge; (iii)To help learners try out new behaviors and acquire new experiences and knowledge in both simulated and “real world” environments (iv)To help learners continue to process experience and knowledge as basis of original knowledge and experience. (v)To help Learners apply new behaviors in “real world” environment”	COMPETENCY BASED CURRICULUM

2. PROBLEM OF STATEMENT

Despite the fact that competency based curriculum is ten years old since its inception in secondary school, there are so many studies which have been done to investigate the way it is implemented in secondary schools. One study on Tanzania done on mass failure of students in recent years in the National Examination found that the curriculum has always been poorly implemented because the majority of stake holders did not aptly understand the requirements of educational guidelines(Rweyemamu,2012). On the other

hand another study done by Woods(2007) points out that, although the Secondary Education Development Program(SEDP) shows that teachers training is a priority and steps are required to provide for a well educated,professional, and skilled teaching force, but no one done study on parents and community awareness about the program because the teacher spend with students only 8 hours at school per day and other 16 hours student spent them with their parents and community.

Another study done by (Alphonse, 2008) have reported a serious shortage of qualified teachers to guide the learners through new learning style and the absence of assessment and examination regime able to reinforce the new approach, also another study was done on the compatibility between teaching methods and Competence-Based curriculum (Tilya & Mafumiko, 2018) whereby they focused on investigating the compatibility between the paradigm and teaching methods which basically concerns teachers and students and other stake holders but community are not involved. Many studies has done on teachers who are implementers but they forget to do studies on awareness of community particularly parents who are regarded as first teacher at home to see if they are aware about this phenomenon of competency based curriculum, and this gap is the reason that the present study investigates the awareness of community on competency based curriculum in Tanzania and challenges facing community awareness.

The purpose of this study was to assess community awareness about competency based curriculum. The specific objectives of competence based curriculum were

1. To determine the community awareness of competence of competence based curriculum
2. To investigate if the community knows any objective of competency based curriculum.
3. To determine the challenges facing community based awareness.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to (Richards J.C and Rogers, 2001) hold that the competency based approach focuses on the outcomes of learning. It addresses on what the learners are expected to do rather than on what they are expected to learn about. The CBA advocates defining educational goals in terms of precise measurable descriptions of knowledge, skills and behaviors that students should possess at the end of a course of study. Also (Schneck, 1978) views the Competence based approach as an outcome based instruction that is adaptive to the needs of students, teachers and the community. Competencies describe the students ability to apply basic and other skills to situations that are commonly encountered in everyday life. Therefore, the competency based approach is based on a set of outcomes that are derived from an analysis of tasks typically required of students in life role situations. To (Savage, 1993) the competency based model was defined by the U.S. office of Education as a performance based process leading to demonstrated mastery of basic and life skills necessary for the individual to function proficiently in the society. It is therefore functional approach to education that emphasizes life skills and evaluates mastery of those skills according to actual learner performance. Another scholar (Mrowicki, L., 1986) holds that competencies consist of a description of the essential skills, knowledge, attitudes and behaviors required for effective performance of a real world task or activity. These activities may relate to any domain of

life. However, (Thinkwise, 2007.) defines competency based curriculum as a research-supported curriculum based on the primary goal of defining the critical behaviors needed for effective and superior individual and organizational performance.

Study done by (Kafyulilo, Rugambuka, & Moses, 2013) on implementation of competency based curriculum in Tanzania, they investigated only on the role of teachers pre service teachers and tutors but in their study they did not find out if the parents are aware or have any influence in implementing competency based curriculum.

Also Another study (Tilya & Mafumiko, 2018) focused on the compatibility between teaching methods and competence based curriculum in Tanzania, they only focused on the classroom problems which can hinder effective implementation of competence based curriculum but they did not find out if the community are aware of competence based curriculum.

Also Another study was done (Kavindi, 2014) investigating the implementation of competence-based curriculum in certificate teachers colleges in Tanzania, this study finds out that the shortage of teachers and facilities hinders the implementation of competency based curriculum, so this study focused only on teachers and community awareness were not involved in the study.

In his study (Nkwetisama, 2012) found that if the community does not have a clue of what is in curriculum and what is intended as outcome of study, the objectives of curriculum can't be achieved, but study like this had not be done in Tanzania.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data for this study was obtained through interviews and questionnaires. A total of 15 members were selected purposively and interviewed (they were teachers who have children who are students) and other 35 were given questionnaires. The data from interview were analyzed by using thematic analysis while data from questionnaire were analyzed by using SPSS 21.

5. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

The findings and discussions of this study were presented as per the objectives. These objectives were to determine community awareness of competency based curriculum. To investigate if the parents know the objective of competency based curriculum and to determine the challenge facing community awareness of competency based curriculum.

In summary of gender respondents 50% were female and 50% were male.

6.1 COMMUNITY AWARENESS OF COMPETENCY BASED CURRICULUM.

On the question of understanding of the meaning of competency based curriculum, about 36 correspondents equal to 72% did not know the meaning of competency

based curriculum. Other 14 corresponds equal 28% knows the meaning of competency based curriculum.

6.2 OBJECTIVES OF COMPETENCY BASED CURRICULUM IN TANZANIA.

On the question of competency based curriculum majority of the correspondents 80% didn't know the objectives of Competency based curriculum, they even don't know what is curriculum, what they know is that their children should go to school and given knowledge by teachers, Some of the correspondents 90% they saw teacher as a sole source of knowledge.

One correspondent on interview when asked to say any one objective of competency based curriculum he said that "it is to make their children to know to speak English well so that they can get good job". But 20% of correspondents who most of them are teachers who have children's at secondary schools who I also interviewed them they know the objectives of competency based curriculum.

6.3. CHALLENGES FACING COMMUNITY AWARENESS EDUCATION ON COMPETENCY BASED CURRICULUM.

The question on challenges facing the institution was asked to the 10 correspondents who are parents who work as teachers. Respondents revealed that interference from politician is one problem, there has been interference from some politicians who are not experts of educations and they still think that the mode of education is the same to old one, they measure performance on the basis of examination results, so the schools which have poor results on national examination their head of school are demoted and other teachers to be transferred to outreach schools, so you will find teachers teaching students on the basis of question and answer, like they focus on what will come to the final examination only, memorization. The role of politician here is that they don't use their platform to address the community exactly the type of curriculum being implemented now, and teachers are not given opportunity by authorities to educate the community, telling them what they should expect from their children.

Other challenge which were pinpointed by the respondent were lack of fund to conduct training, They could be invited to the radio and Tv to inform the community what is going on, So if the governments and other stake holders will provide fund for training it will be much better. Another respondent said that government are putting more money in campaign of other community based education awareness like diseases but it is imperative also for the community to know their education system and how it is implemented.

Lack of priority from stake holders and government; The government for long time plus stake holders they didn't see any meaning in making community aware of type of educational curriculum being implemented believing that training only teachers as implementers is enough and

ignoring the parents who spent most of time with their children.

7. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS.

This paper aimed at assessing three specific objectives: To determine community awareness of competency based curriculum, to investigate if the community know any objectives of competency based curriculum and to determine challenge facing community awareness of competency based curriculum. On the aspect of community awareness about 72% did not know the meaning of competency based curriculum. Other corresponds equal 28% knows the meaning of competency based curriculum. These finding suggest that majority of the community they are not aware about the concept of concept of competency based curriculum, this could be because of low or lack of emphasis on community awareness of type of curriculum being implemented.

On the aspect of objectives of competency based curriculum 80% didn't know the objectives of Competency based curriculum, what they know is that their children should go to school and given knowledge by teachers, Other 90% they saw teacher as a sole source of knowledge and also added that the objective is let their children know English language and get better jobs when they finish school. This finding shows that in order to have best results of competency based curriculum society should be awakened.

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